

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.153 Max: 62.182 <i>From SU 1460</i>	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1458 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #: 1985-88	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:	
DEFINITION <i>Upper fill of imbrex grave</i>				Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1385	Fills <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1461	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX clay 15% silt 80% sand 5%	
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery f <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft
				Color		<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						
Northern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original		
Southern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
Western Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
Eastern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to:				Is bound to (only for masonry):		
Is abutted by:				Abuts:		
Is covered by: 1385				Covers: 1392, 1459		
Is cut by:				Cuts:		
Is filled by:				Fills: 1461		
OBSERVATIONS <i>excavated by trowel, dry conditions, the fill was in terms of soil not different from SU 1385, but contained older pottery.</i>						
DESCRIPTION						
Position within sector: <i>central</i>						
Shape: <i>rectangular, conforms to shape of cut 1461</i>						
For layers complete this section:						
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): <i>flat, no visible inclusions</i>						
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope) <i>no clusters</i>						
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):						
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)						
For cuts complete this section:				Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):		
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight						
Cut sides <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping						
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular						
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded						
Observations:						

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

upper fill of a grave, an infant burial within two inches, the fill was in terms of soil not different to 1385 but some instinct made the excavators separate the finds from this deeper area (they said the pottery seemed to be different to what they found above.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by *T. Hart*

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Entered by

on